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On the cover page from left to right:
Prince Vladimir Monomakh, the Emperor Nicholas II is in the centre, the Princess Olga
At the bottom of the cover page: Chernomorskay Gubernia (Black Sea Province) emblem
and photo “Views of the Russian Empire. Riga”

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Annual Publications of the Arkhangelsk Provincial Statistical Committee as a Source on the Socio-Economic Development of the Arkhangelsk Province in the Period 1876–1900

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Abstract

The article considers a group of annual publications of the Arkhangelsk Provincial Statistical Committee of the period 1876–1900.

The source base of the study consists of time-based publications of the Arkhangelsk Provincial Statistical Committee of the period 1876–1900. Most of these publications are presented by the annual reports of the Arkhangelsk Provincial Statistical Committee. Besides this, the “Reference Book of the Arkhangelsk Province” and “Proceedings of the Arkhangelsk Provincial Statistical Committee” were published once, as well as the “Commemorative Books of the Arkhangelsk Province” and “Address Calendars of the Arkhangelsk Province” were occasionally published.

In conclusion, the authors state that the 25th anniversary from 1876 to 1900 was marked by a significant reduction in the research work of the Arkhangelsk Statistical Committee. So, if in 1850–1875 about 90 scientific research papers were published, then in 1876–1900 their number decreased by 4 times (excluding individual publications), that is, to 22. This reduction was due to the fact that alternative and more mass-produced periodicals (for example, newspapers) began to appear in the province, which began to allocate a significant number of their strips for research works on the Arkhangelsk province. It is also important to note that in the period 1876–1900 there was a reduction in the publications published by the committee. Thus, the Arkhangelsk Collection ceases to be published, and only once in 25 years have the Reference Book of the Arkhangelsk Province and the Proceedings of the Arkhangelsk Provincial Statistical Committee been published.

Keywords: socio-economic development, Arkhangelsk province, Russian Empire, sustainable development of regions, 1876–1900, annual publications, Arkhangelsk Provincial Statistical Committee.

1. Введение

В дореволюционный период региональным статистическим комитетам отводилась центральная роль в организации локальных исторических исследований. Причин этому было много, однако самой главной было то, что именно в местные статистические комитеты стекалась первичная информация о состоянии социально-экономической жизни в губернии. Чиновники этого ведомства и сводили эти сведения в общегубернские списки, что приводило к систематизации обширной статистической информации, которая впоследствии (после публикации) в местной печати создавала первые наработки в историографическом освещении тех или иных вопросов. В данном исследовании мы

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Mikhailov, 1878 – *Mikhailov, V.V.* (1878). Statisticheskoe opisanie Arkhangel'skoi gubernii za 1876 g. [Statistical description of the Arkhangel'sk province for 1876]. Otchet gubernskogo statisticheskogo komiteta. Arkhangel'sk. [in Russian]

Mikhailov, 1879 – *Mikhailov, V.V.* (1879). Statisticheskoe opisanie Arkhangel'skoi gubernii za 1877 g. [Statistical description of the Arkhangel'sk province for 1877]. Otchet gubernskogo statisticheskogo komiteta. Arkhangel'sk. [in Russian]

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Chudov, 2015 – *Chudov, S.I.* (2015). Uroven' obespecheniya prodovol'stvennoi bezopasnosti na russkom Severe v XIX – nachale XX veka [Level of food security in the Russian North in the 19th – early 20th centuries]. *Istoricheskie, filosofskie, politicheskie i yuridicheskie nauki, kul'turologiya i iskusstvovedenie. Voprosy teorii i praktiki.* 7-1 (57): 194-197. [in Russian]

Magsumov et al., 2023 – *Magsumov, T.A., Zulfugarzade, T.E., Kolotkov, M.B., Zinkovskii, S.B.* (2023). Annual Publications of the Arkhangel'sk Provincial Statistical Committee as a Source on the Socio-Economic Development of the Arkhangel'sk Province in the Period 1850–1875. *Bylye Gody.* 18(3): 1207-1218.

Magsumov et al., 2023a – *Magsumov, T.A., Zulfugarzade, T.E., Kolotkov, M.B., Zinkovskii, S.B.* (2023). Yearly Publications Produced by the Arkhangel'sk Gubernia Statistics Committee as a Source on Socio-Economic Development of the Arkhangel'sk Governorate in early 20th century. *European Journal of Contemporary Education.* 12(3): 1082-1089.

Ежегодные издания Архангельского губернского статистического комитета как источник по социально-экономическому развитию Архангельской губернии периода 1876–1900 гг.

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается группа ежегодных изданий Архангельского губернского статистического комитета периода 1876–1900 гг.

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Источниковая база исследования состоит из повременных изданий Архангельского губернского статистического комитета периода 1876–1900 гг. Большинство таких изданий представлено ежегодными отчетами архангельского губернского статистического комитета. Помимо этого, единожды публиковались «Справочная книжка Архангельской губернии» и «Труды Архангельского губернского статистического комитета», а также эпизодично публиковались «Памятные книжки Архангельской губернии» и «Адрес-календари Архангельской губернии».

В заключении авторы отмечают, что 25-летие с 1876 по 1900 гг. ознаменовалось значительным сокращением научно-исследовательской работы Архангельского статистического комитета. Так, если в 1850–1875 гг. было опубликовано около 90 научно-исследовательских работ, то в 1876–1900 гг. их количество сократилось в 4 раза (без учета отдельных изданий), то есть до 22. Такое сокращение было связано с тем, что в губернии начали появляться альтернативные и более массовые периодические издания (например, газеты), которые для научно-исследовательских работ, посвященных Архангельской губернии, стали выделять значительное количество своих полос. Также важно отметить, что в период с 1876 по 1900 гг. происходит сокращение издаваемых комитетом изданий. Так, перестает издаваться «Архангельский сборник», и только по одному разу за 25 лет вышли «Справочная книжка Архангельской губернии» и «Труды Архангельского губернского статистического комитета».

Ключевые слова: социально-экономическое развитие, Архангельская губерния, Российская империя, устойчивое развитие регионов, 1876–1900 гг., ежегодные издания, Архангельский губернский статистический комитет.